

OPTIMIZING OF MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR PREGNANT WOMEN WITH ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA TO IMPROVE PERINATAL OUTCOMES

Bekbaulieva Gulistan Niyatbayevna

Professor, MD.

Rasuljonova Zulfizar Zokhidjon kizi

Student of Tashkent state medical university

e-mail: zulfizar01r@icloud.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19273775>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23rd March 2026

Accepted: 25th March 2026

Online: 27th March 2026

KEYWORDS

Objective: To study pregnancy complications and delivery outcomes in women with ASB and to develop preventive measures by optimizing their management

ABSTRACT

Urinary tract infections are the second most common after acute respiratory viral infections and rank second in the structure of somatic pathology during pregnancy after cardiovascular diseases.

Urinary tract infections are the second most common after acute respiratory viral infections and rank second in the structure of somatic pathology during pregnancy after cardiovascular diseases. Despite being a subclinical condition, asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) increases the risk of gestational pyelonephritis by 20–30 times and is associated with preterm birth and low birth weight. The difficulty of selecting antimicrobial therapy due to potential fetal risks determines the relevance of this problem.

Objective: To study pregnancy complications and delivery outcomes in women with ASB and to develop preventive measures by optimizing their management.

The study consisted of three stages.

Stage I: Retrospective analysis of 150 case histories to identify risk factors and clinical characteristics.

Stage II: Prospective observation of pregnant women with different microbial loads: a study group (n=30, 10³–10⁴ CFU/ml) and a comparison group (n=38, 10⁵ CFU/ml).

Stage III: Clinical evaluation of treatment efficacy in 60 pregnant women: standard therapy (n=30) versus complex therapy including proanthocyanidins (n=30).

Methods included obstetric and gynecological assessment, general clinical examination, and microbiological urine culture with sensitivity testing.

The main risk factors identified were ASB (29.6%), bacterial vaginosis (15.3%), low social status (7.2%), tonsillitis (11.2–15.3%), and living conditions (rural residence without registration — 8%, temporary registration — 2.7%).

Implementation of complex therapy significantly reduced gestational and perinatal complications. A decrease was observed in gestational pyelonephritis, preeclampsia, fetal loss,

premature rupture of membranes, preterm birth, birth trauma, and purulent-septic complications.

In women with ASB, pregnancy complications occurred 3 times more often, labor complications 7 times more often, and placental and fetal membrane pathology 5 times more often compared to women without bacteriuria, largely due to the absence of antibacterial therapy.

The proposed treatment method reduced pregnancy complications by 1.5 times and preterm birth by 2 times.

Conclusions: ASB is a major risk factor for gestational pyelonephritis and adverse perinatal outcomes. Optimized комплекс therapy including antibacterial treatment and proanthocyanidins improves outcomes.

Recommendations: All pregnant women should undergo bacteriological urine screening for ASB. Women with risk factors should be rescreened in the 2nd and 3rd trimesters. Confirmed ASB requires oral antibacterial therapy based on microbial sensitivity in combination with proanthocyanidins.

